

ON THE PREPARATION OF ETHYL β -ETHOXYPROPIONATE

By M. SWAMINATHAN

The preparation of ethyl β -ethoxypropionate in quantity is of great commercial importance as it is one of the starting materials for the manufacture of vitamin-B₁, according to the method of Williams and his colleagues (Cline, Williams and Finkelstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1052). A survey of the literature revealed that only a few reports have appeared in the past on the preparation of β -ethoxypropionic acid or its ester (Purdie and Marshall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 475; Jones and Powers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2529; Cramer, Hunter and Hibbert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 513; B.P. 498738). As the starting materials required for the above methods were not available in this country at the time this work was done, an alternative method for the preparation of ethyl β -ethoxypropionate was explored. The possibility of preparing the compound by the action of sodium ethoxide on ethyl β -bromopropionate was tried as ethyl β -bromopropionate can be easily prepared starting from ethylene chlorohydrin according to the methods given in "Organic Synthesis" (Kendall and McKenzie, Vol. III, pp. 25, 51, 57). The present note describes the conditions which give high yields of ethyl β -ethoxypropionate (80-85% of the theory) on the basis of ethyl β -bromopropionate used.

Ethyl β -Ethoxypropionate.—Sodium (23 g., 1 gram atom) cut into pieces was added in small quantities at a time through one of the side necks of a 3-necked 1000 c.c. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel containing 400 c.c. of absolute alcohol. When the sodium had completely dissolved, the mixture was cooled in ice-water. Ethyl β -bromopropionate (90.5 g., $\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) was added in 10 c.c. portions with constant shaking. The addition of the bromo-ester was completed in 15 minutes. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight in cold water at room temperature and then heated for 2 hours on a steam-bath. Part of the ester was hydrolysed during this process. Sodium hydroxide (100 c.c., 20%) was then added and the mixture heated for one hour on the water-bath to hydrolyse completely all the ester. The mixture was cooled, just neutralised by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid and then made slightly alkaline to litmus by the addition of a few drops of sodium hydroxide (20%). The alcohol and water were distilled off on the water-bath under diminished pressure. The residue was taken up in 50 c.c. of water, acidified by the addition of sufficient concentrated hydrochloric acid (about 55 to 60 c.c. may be required till the mixture was acid to thymol blue) and saturated with sodium chloride when a greater portion of β -ethoxypropionic acid separated as an oil. The acid was separated and the aqueous layer extracted thrice with ether (100 c.c. each time). The ether extracts were mixed with the main bulk of the β -ethoxypropionic acid, dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed by distillation. The residue was dissolved in absolute alcohol (150 c.c.) and converted into the ester, following exactly the procedure described for the preparation of ethyl ethoxyacetate ('Organic Synthesis', Vol. XIII, p. 42). The yield of the ester boiling at 166° at 755 m.m. was 65 g. (88% of the theory based on

ethyl β -bromopropionate used). The ester is quite pure and can be used straight-away for further synthetic operations.

In many typical experiments the yield ranged from 75 to 85% of the theory. The quantity of sodium ethoxide used affects the yields considerably. Good yields are obtained only by using 2 to 2.5 g. atoms of sodium for one molecule of ethyl β -bromopropionate. When only one gram atom of sodium (which is just the theoretical amount necessary) was used, the yields were very low, 20 to 25% presumably due to the formation of ethyl acrylate as a by-product. Excess of sodium ethoxide present presumably reacts with ethyl acrylate formed converting it into ethyl β -ethoxypropionate as observed by Purdie and Marshall (*loc. cit.*).

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A NOTE ON THE IODOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF TRIVALENT ANTIMONY

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The method of Dunstan and Boole (*Pharm. J.*, 1889, 19, 385) for the iodometric estimation of trivalent antimony, in which sodium bicarbonate is used to neutralise the acid formed in the course of the reaction, suffers from the serious defect that if the titration is not finished quickly, antimonious oxide comes down as a precipitate. This is due to the neutralisation of the tartaric acid by sodium bicarbonate. It was thought that if sodium acetate was used, no neutralisation of the tartaric acid would take place and the titration could be carried smoothly; but it was found that a very slight precipitation of antimonious oxide did take place. So small amounts of acetic acid were added to the solution containing tartar emetic and sodium acetate and no precipitation took place even if traces of acetic acid were present. As expected it was found that the reverse reaction, the reduction of antimonic acid by hydriodic acid, took place if the concentration of hydrogen ion was large, but up to a concentration of $N/32$ (in the solution to be titrated) there was no sign of the above reverse reaction having taken place.

The following is the summary of experimental results. 25 C.c. of $N/10$ tartar emetic were taken and 5 g. of sodium acetate were added in every case. The strength of the acetic acid which differed from solution to solution is indicated by [HAc] and the volume of iodine used is indicated by "V" in case of all the experiments.

[HAc] "V"	N	N/2	N/4	N/8	N/10	N/32	N/64	0
	18.1	18.15	18.2	18.2	18.2	18.25	18.25	18.25

At room temperature sodium bicarbonate method and sodium acetate-acetic acid method yield the same results. Only the titration is easier in the second case and one has not to hurry up.

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